

Mount Putuo 普陀山

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Made up of elite and non-elite pilgrims, imperial patrons, and monks, devotees of Guanyin legitimated Mount Putuo as a sacred site as well as the home of the Bodhisattva. Not part of a codified sect of religious practitioners, this group helped domesticate Guanyin at Mount Putuo while also establishing it as the mythical potalaka from the Huayan (Flower Garland) Sutra. Potalaka (補陀落山) refers to the home of the Bodhisattva who perceives the world's sounds (Guānshīyīn 觀世音 -- the Chinese translation of Avalokiteśvara). Compared to other Buddhist pilgrimage sites, Mount Putuo's emergence as a national and international place of pilgrimage was late. It began in the tenth century, and in the 16th century gained more traction. It was after the 18th century that it reached its peak in popularity. Other famous Buddhist mountains, such as Mounts Wutai and Emei were popularized during the Tang Dynasty. For Putuo, trade at the location was important for its establishment, as were miracle tales. Stories that located Guanyin at the site, and connected the mountain with the notion of potalaka, helped build the site as a Buddhist pilgrimage destination. Miracle tales have been essential for Mount Putuo's development, as they provided the mystique that draws in visitors. As Marcus Bingenheimer (2016) notes in his examination of Mount Putuo gazetteers, in the Ming and Qing eras, tales of supernatural events occurring at Mount Putuo were part of the religious 'imaginaire' regarding the site. These included accounts of individuals receiving a vision of the Bodhisattva, plus efficacious wonders (miracles) performed by Guanyin. The work by Chūn-fang Yū (2001) regarding Guanyin and Mount Putuo further confirms the importance of miracle tales in sacralizing Mount Putuo as the home of Guanyin. Throughout its history, the location has been shaped by government impositions on religion, military activities, elite (literati) and non-elite pilgrims, and national and international trade. In the modern era, Mount Putuo has been greatly influenced by economic investments in religious sites. Each of China's four Buddhist mountains has a government-operated tourism corporation, and the Mount Putuo Tourism Development Company is one example of the kind of corporatization that shapes Chinese Buddhism today. Tourism development companies function as private operators, but they are officially state-owned. Thus, although the Chinese government is an atheist state, it is a patron of Buddhism. After the death of Mao, reforms regarding religious and economic policies occurred, and in 1982, religious policy began protecting five legal religions -- Buddhism, Daoism, Protestantism, Catholicism, and Islam. Throughout Chinese Buddhism's history, financial donations from laity, as well as donations of land, have supported monastic communities and temples, but since the 1990s, local governments have also become donors of Buddhism through their support and initiation of building or rebuilding of Buddhist sites. Local governments are interested in these efforts for the economic benefits that can come from tourism. Interestingly, even in its contemporary setting, Mount Putuo's miracle tales are significant for its identity. In current tourism advertisements, miracle tales are used to draw in visitors, and tourist organizations promote the site for its efficacious mystique. Thus even within state-sponsored tourism, the location is a center for encountering Buddhist culture and the Bodhisattva Guanyin.

Date Range: 1978 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Putuo Mountain

Region tags: China, East Asia

Putuo Mountain, located near Zhoushan Island.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Island of Guanyin: Mount Putuo and Its Gazetteers
- Source 2: Kuan-yin : the Chinese transformation of Avalokitesivara
- Source 3: Religion as Financial Asset: State Investments in Chinese Buddhism
- Source 1: The General and the Bodhisattva: Commander Hou Jigao Travels to Mount Putuo
- Source 2: Legends, Inspirations and Space: Landscape Sacralization of the Sacred Site Mount Putuo
- Source 3: Buddhism and Tourism: Perceptions of the Monastic Community at Pu-Tuo-Shan, China
- Source 1: Administering Bodhisattva Guanyin's island: the Monasteries, political entities, and power holders of Putuoshan
- Source 2: Legends, Inspirations and Space: Landscape Sacralization of the Sacred Site Mount Putuo
- Source 3: Putuoshan Wenhua Shi. 普陀山文化史.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.buddhistdoor.net/features/mount-putuo-wonders-and-thoughts/>
- Source 1 Description: An online Buddhist journal providing a diverse range of English-language Buddhist content.
- Source 2 URL: <https://oxfordre.com/religion/display/10.1093/acrefore/9780199340378.001.0001/acrefore-9780199340378-e-702;jsessionid=3EA730321CD8F0CE937726D04B0D7362?rskey=jVnmyQ&result=7>
- Source 2 Description: Oxford Research Encyclopedias provides in-depth, peer-reviewed summaries.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.putuo.org.cn>
- Source 3 Description: Website of the Buddhist Association of Mount Putuo.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: http://www.cttbusa.org/avatamsaka/avatamsaka_contents.asp.html
- Source 1 Description: Avatamsaka Sutra Translated by Buddhist Text Translation Society

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The historical development of Buddhism in China included interactions between Daoist and Buddhist ideas. Various Daoist perspectives, including those associated with mountains, influenced Chinese Buddhism.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: To become an ordained Buddhist monk or nun, one needs to go through a standard procedure. However, lay Buddhism in China today is organized in a variety of ways -- associations, schools, conferences, and textual publications.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: While participating in Buddhist activities at Mount Putuo does not necessitate "belonging" or "identifying" as Buddhism, the monastic Buddhist Association of Mount Putuo supports developing the regional area to create multiple opportunities to engage in Buddhist study and practice. In addition to new temples being built, colleges have been established for the study of Buddhism. This active involvement in infrastructure is part of spreading interest in Buddhist study and practice, and the Buddhist Association of Mount Putuo actively promotes the spread of Guanyin "culture."

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: Through state-own tourism development companies, the state participates in paying for infrastructure. Additionally, in the early 1980s, reconstruction of Mount Putuo was initiated by Zhang Jinfu -- an official.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: In contemporary China, Buddhist mountains have been revitalized through the help of state-owned tourism corporations. They have been developed with the hopes of boosting tourism.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In contemporary settings, the monastic Buddhist Association of Mount Putuo is the supervising body of the sacred mountain. On August 9th, 2021, the association held its 7th Representative meeting at Puji Zen Temple with 130 representatives attending. Each year, millions of visitors travel to the sacred site, but visitors do not need to identify as "Buddhist."

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: Contemporary Chinese Buddhism is organized with official, monastic organizations (in this case the Buddhist Association of Mount Putuo), plus lay Buddhists (居士jushi) who participate in Buddhist activities. Lay Buddhists in China are organized by meetings such as dharma assemblies, conferences, publications, and Buddhist study.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

Notes: In June 1948, the Mount Putuo Branch of the Buddhist Association of China was established, and after the association of Mount Putuo was restored in 1980, Venerable Miaoshan was elected as the chairperson. In 2010, Venerable Daoci was elected as the most recent chairperson of the monastic association.

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: From the standpoint of Buddhism's four sacred mountains, each has its own administrative body that is a local representation of the national Buddhist Association of China.

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

Notes: Within Buddhist Associations affiliated with a particular location, there are leaders who oversee the religious functions and practices of temples and monasteries.

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

Notes: There is a head leader of the Buddhist Association of Mount Putuo, but the location and its Buddhist activities are also shaped by the United Front Work Department and the Religious Affairs Bureau.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: The association functions as a group of leaders, but they are led by a head monk.

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 3

Notes: Administration at Mount Putuo is complicated -- the United Front Work Department, the Religious Affairs Bureau, and the Buddhist Association shape the location. The Buddhist Association regulated religious practices, and the Buddhist Association of Mount Putuo is a local branch of the national organization.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

Notes: As detailed in Claire Vidal's "Administering Bodhisattva Guanyin's Island," leadership often comes through social connections that individuals make, and leaders are appointed. Buddhist associations are led by an official chair plus a group of vice-chairs.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist leaders (and leadership) are subject to three layers of oversight -- the Buddhist Association of China (a nongovernmental organization that works closely with state agencies to guide the development of the religion); the State Administration for Religious Affairs, and the CCP's United Front Work Department, responsible for managing relations with nonparty entities. Monastics who criticize the political system have faced surveillance, travel restrictions, and even imprisonment. It is not uncommon for temples to be run jointly by monastics and a temple administration committee that is connected to the local Religious Affairs Bureau. Leadership decisions are made with this oversight.

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– Yes

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– I don't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: There are many Buddhist scriptures that are connected with the Bodhisattva Guanyin herself. There are more than 80 sutras in which she appears, and this does not capture esoteric sutras connected with her that amount to 88. One of the central scriptures glorifying the bodhisattva is the Lotus Sutra. In the Shurangama Sutra, the bodhisattva has many heads, arms, and eyes, and in the esoteric sutras, the bodhisattva teaches saving dharanis. Mount Putuo has its own set of texts called gazetteers, which are a form of Chinese writing that includes cultural and topographic descriptions with local historiography. These are important primary resources for revealing the transformation of the island into Guanine's potalaka.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Local legends and oral stories were integral to the transformation of the island into Guanyin's potalaka. These stories included visualizations of Guanyin at the mountain, and

overtime, miracle tales were recorded in the mountain's gazetteers.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

Notes: Historically, the translation and thus interpretation of scriptures was performed by monastics, but in a modern emergence of lay Buddhism, scriptures are interpreted

by lay Buddhists.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 33

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– I don't know

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Nanhai Guanyin -- Statue of the Bodhisattva Guanyin

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Across the island, there are depictions of Buddhas, Bodhisattvas, and Dharma Protectors.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Portrayals of well-known pilgrims are one example.

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Chan Buddhist temples themselves are oriented for positive Feng shui. They are designed to be on the north-south axis for optimum qi.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Notes: Pilgrims choose to traverse the island for a variety of reasons. Some are seeking merit for a better rebirth or rebirth in the pure land, but many are on pilgrimage to have a positive outcome in this life -- a strong college entrance exam score for a loved one, wealth and success in business, or pregnancy.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– No

Notes: It depends on the school of Buddhism that is answering this question, but there is the notion that karmic energy is created by speech and physical acts, as well as the mind, which all influences the next life -- the rebirth that consciousness takes.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

Notes: It is understood that the spirit-mind of enlightened beings can be attached to materials, i.e., the statue of a Buddha or Bodhisattva emanates the powers of enlightenment from that enlightened being.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist teachings include the belief in six possible realms of existence while in samsara (rebirth) -- realm of the gods (heavens), realm of the demi-gods, realm of humans, realm of animals, realm of hungry ghosts, and realm of demons (hells). Beyond this is Amitabha's Western Pure Land -- a realm outside the confines of samsaric existence that is possible for rebirth for those who entrust their faith in Amitabha to be reborn there. It is believed that one's merit (and the sending of merit from others) can help someone reach the Pure Land after death, which is desirable because it is easier to reach enlightenment there, outside the confines of samsara.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

Notes: Buddhism accounts for "above" realms in terms of suffering, but these are not vague. Instead, they are clearly described as realms with less suffering.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

Notes: Buddhism accounts for "below" realms in terms of suffering, but these are not vague. Instead, they are clearly described as realms with greater suffering.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: Rebirth again as a human would be seen as a horizontal rebirth, but if conditions for reaching enlightenment were improved or diminished in the next life as a human, then it would be "above" or "below" current existence.

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: The Western Pure Land is an "other" space -- a realm outside samsara.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhism believes in possible rebirth as an animal but not a plant.

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: One's collected karmic energy is what creates future forms of life.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: Within Samsaric existence, one can be reborn in the realm of gods, demi-gods, humans, animals, hungry ghosts, and demons (hells).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– Yes

Notes: Some traditions believe in the ability to mummify oneself. through dehydrating the body, and meditating, some monks have self-mummified.

↳ Interment:

– I don't know

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Funeral ceremonies in traditional Chinese practices last over 49 days, with prayers said every seven days for 49 days, if the family is able to afford this to occur.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: throughout its history, Chinese Buddhism has consisted of monasteries with icons of Buddhas and Bodhisattvas, as well as enlightened masters. It is believed that these portraiture or statues of enlightened beings carry with them the presence of the individual, plus their power of enlightenment.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: It is believed by practitioners that the Bodhisattva Guanyin's presence is at Mount Putuo, and she has manifested herself to practitioners who visit there. However, Guanyin is not a "high God" but rather an exemplar for someone on the Bodhisattva path.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - No
 - Notes: Miracles note the Bodhisattva Guanyin's presence at Mount Putuo, but given her identity as the Bodhisattva of Compassion, she is known for effecting positive changes to one's life and not negative ones.
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Guanyin is seen as a compassionate being who can manifest in any form, to come to the aid of a practitioner.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

Notes: This is a challenging question to answer because throughout Chinese Buddhism's history, there has been a wide swath of imaginings regarding the Buddhas and Bodhisattvas. At times, the historical Buddha is seen as a central, prominent position, but at other times, it is Amitabha Buddha.

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Buddhas and Bodhisattvas have different skills or arenas they dominate. Amitabha oversees the Western Pure Land and Bhaisajyaguru is known as the Healing Buddha. Guanyin is the Bodhisattva of Compassion, accessible to anyone who calls upon her.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhas and Bodhisattvas are believed to have the ability to intervene and respond, based on practitioner effort.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The law of karma acts in this way. Through the acquisition of merit (good/positive karma), it is believed that the effect is less suffering.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: For self transformation purposes -- moving from delusion to enlightenment -- ritual and devotion are part of Chinese Buddhist schools, which involve the interaction with Buddhas and Bodhisattvas.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Rebirth in the Western Pure Land, as the result of devotion, practice, and ritual, is emphasized as a result.

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Pure Land Sutras describe it as a desirable place in terms of sensory enjoyment.

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Identifying if the Pure Land is mild or extreme sensory pleasure is challenging, but it is indeed viewed as a place of enjoyment for the senses.

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:
 - No

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:
 - Yes
 - Notes: If one is reborn into the Western Pure Land, it is believed they will more easily reach enlightenment -- become a Buddha or Bodhisattva there, which is considered "superior" than being a human.

- ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Yes, through devotion, one can reach the Pure Land.

- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes

Notes: Success in business is included in what pilgrims hope for as a result of devotion and pilgrimage.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There is a range of practice from pilgrims who are at Mount Putuo, but some might practice the five precepts more closely while there. These include refraining from stealing, lying, sexual misconduct, intoxicants, and killing. With the last of killing, some pilgrims will follow vegetarianism more closely, if they do not already.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– No

↳ Courage (generic):

– I don't know

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– No

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Non-violence

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Not by lay Buddhists, but celibacy is required of monks and nuns.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Monogamy (males):

– No

Monogamy (females):

– No

Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: One of the five precepts is to abstain from sexual misconduct, which is often taught as non-consensual sex.

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: One of the five precepts is to abstain from sexual misconduct, which is often taught as non-consensual sex.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: Not required for lay Buddhists, but monastic communities will engage in fasting, in the form of reducing the number of meals taken each day.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Not for lay Buddhists, but monastics will refrain from garlic and onions. Monastics are also vegetarian, and some lay Buddhists will choose to eat this way as well.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Monastic communities follow a strict schedule regarding time each day (eating, prayer, fasting, chanting), but lay Buddhists are not required to follow this structure.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: There are five precepts that are taught to lay Buddhists, with many more for monastics. They include refraining from killing, stealing, lying, sexual misconducts, and intoxication.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Not required, but many lay Chinese Buddhists keep a home shrine in which they honor their deceased family members.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: Not required, but lay Buddhists at Mount Putuo often consider themselves “pilgrims,” and are on a ritual of devotion.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A nation-state.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– I don't know

Notes: Providing institutionalized poverty relief is tricky in Modern China because Buddhist communities cannot appear as though they are questioning the government's stance on human rights.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: At Mount Putuo, there is a Buddhist College.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than

the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: Lay Buddhists may not be aware of the intricacies of interactions between the monastic community and government institutions.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– I don't know

Notes: This would depend on the individual person under examination, and their relationship to the Party.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: There is not public food storage available at Mount Putuo.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Not within the confines of Mount Putuo.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Transportation infrastructure is provided by the island's tourism operations.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Only in the case of breaking a law.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: At most extreme, going against Party policies could result in this.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Monks and nuns follow monastic codes of conduct, but lay Buddhists can choose their level of involvement with the five precepts.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Practitioners (both lay and monastic) must adhere to the government's legal code.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Monastic and lay activity must follow government laws, and if this is not done so, the police (which is a Chinese paramilitary organization) will become involved.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Monastic and lay Buddhists at Mount Putuo use standardized mandarin for communications.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Calendar events include auspicious days, and at Mount Putuo, these are connected to significant events of the Bodhisattva Guanyin (birthday, day of enlightenment, day of renunciation).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Monastic and lay Buddhists follow the Chinese calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Lay communities provide food for monastic communities, and this involvement is

differentiated by the particular lay Buddhists involved. But generally, we can think of this in terms of gathering food and possibly providing food from their own small-scale agriculture.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Mount Putuo 普陀山, Bingenheimer, Marcus. *Island of Guanyin: Mount Putuo and Its Gazetteers*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016.

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